

DAMAGE IN GLASS/EPOXY PLATES UNDER COMBINED TENSION-TORSION LOADING

X.L.Gong, A.Laksimi, D.Lai and M.L.Benzeggagh

Université de Technologie de Compiègne, LG2mS URA CNRS 1505
Centre de recherche, BP. 649, 60206 Compiègne FRANCE

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to determine analytically the stress fields, the damage initiation and its prediction by Tsai-Wu criteria and the evolution of damage state using various parameters, such as stiffness parameter D ($D=1-C/C_0$ in tension and $D=1-G_{12}^0/G_{12}$ in torsion), R_{ij} (Damage Participation Rate) based on an acoustic emission model. Their relationships with the different damage mechanisms are also discussed so as to give some useful information in improvement of the strength in composite structures.

KEY-WORDS : plate, combined tension-torsion, stress analysis, damage, acoustic emission

INTRODUCTION

Damage in composite materials reduces the strength and the stiffness and determines the life of composite structures. The study of their basic mechanisms, accumulation and characterization is certainly very interesting to improve the mechanical behaviour of these materials. Various studies [1,2,3] concerning the damage state in composite plates loaded uniaxially (tension, compression, bending ...) were conducted with success. But for general loading conditions which are subjected by the real engineering structures, the damage state is more difficult to predict and a lot of efforts have to be given. After a damage study of a composite plate in tension [4] and in torsion [5], this paper describes the damage mechanisms in an unidirectional composite plates under combined tension-torsion loading.

STRESS ANALYSIS

(a) Stress distribution

In the order to apply simultaneously a torque moment (M_a) and a tension (P), the extremities of an unidirectional composite plate are embedded in the grips. One of grips is fixed and the other is moving in rotation and in axial displacement (x) (Fig.1).

Fig.1 Schema of a plate constrained on the combined tension-torsion loading

In this case, the end subjected to the twisting moments and the tension to have the same displacement in the direction of the laminate axis x, each fiber will deform differently due to their different distance from the specimen axis (x). The farthest from the axis (x) fibers are, the more they try to extend and compatibility of laminate deformation is enforced by additional normal stresses in the fiber direction. So a normal stress is produced in the fiber direction, it is composed of two parts, one due to the torsion $\sigma_{11}(\phi, y)$ and other due to the tension $\sigma_{11}(P)$:

$$\sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P) = \sigma_{11}(\phi, y) + \sigma_{11}(P) \quad (1)$$

Assuming that the laminate thickness (b) is too small to be taken into account and the laminate width (w) is constant during test, the analytical solution of the first part $\sigma_{11}(\phi, y)$ was given in accordance with a precedent study for pure torsion by Gong and al [5]. In the case of combined tension-torsion loading, the fiber deformations are function of the twisting angle "φ", the position "y" and the applied force "P". The normal stress $\sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P)$ due to this combined loading can be expressed by :

$$\sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P) = E_{11} \epsilon_{11}(\phi, y, P) = E_{11} \frac{\sqrt{L'^2 + \phi^2 y^2} - L}{L} \quad (2)$$

where L' is instantaneous specimen length with rotation (L' > L) depending on the angle φ and on the applied force P. The following relationship allows to determine L' :

$$\frac{EbL'W}{2L} - \frac{EbL'}{\phi} \left[\text{Ln} \left(\frac{(\frac{W}{2}) + \sqrt{(\frac{W}{2})^2 + (L'/\phi)^2}}{L'/\phi} \right) \right] = P \quad (3)$$

where b and w are thickness and width of specimen respectively.

So, the stress state in 3D results from three stresses $\sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P)$, τ_{12} and τ_{13} , which the normal stress $\sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P)$ due to combined tension-torsion can be determined by equations 2 and 3. The maximum tension stress is reached at the ends of the specimen and the minimum at the center of the specimen (Fig.2). Their ratio depend on the force/moment (P/M). The maximum shear stresses $\tau_{12\text{max}}$ and $\tau_{13\text{max}}$ can be obtained by the effective moment.

Fig.2 Stress $\sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P)$ distribution under combined tension-torsion loading

(b) Effective moment (M_{eff})

The applied moment M_{app} consists also of two parts :

$$M_{\text{app}} = M' + M_{\text{eff}} \quad (4)$$

where M' is additional moment determined by following relationship :

$$M' = 2 \int_0^{w/2} y \sigma_{11}(\phi, y, P) \sin \alpha(y) b dy = 2 E_{11} b \int_0^{w/2} \left[\frac{\phi y^2}{L} - \frac{y^2}{\sqrt{(\frac{L'}{\phi})^2 + y^2}} \right] dy$$

$$M' = \frac{Eb\phi W^3}{12 L} - \frac{EbW}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{L'}{\phi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{W}{2}\right)^2} + Eb \left(\frac{L'}{\phi}\right)^2 \text{Ln} \left[\frac{W\phi}{2L'} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{W\phi}{2L'}\right)^2} \right] \quad (5)$$

In fact, one part of the M_{app} has to equilibrate the additional moment M' caused by the normal stress $\sigma_{11}(\varphi, y, P)$, only the rest M_{eff} can be used to determine shear stresses τ_{12max} and τ_{13max} . Introducing the effective moment M_{eff} in the Lekhnitskii's theory [6], we obtain :

$$\tau_{12max} = \frac{M_{eff}}{Wb^2} k_1 \quad (6)$$

$$\tau_{13max} = \frac{M_{eff}}{Wb^2} \sqrt{\frac{G_{13}}{G_{12}}} k_2 \quad (7)$$

These analyses are independent of the materials. If the rotation displacement is important, the normal stress and the additional moment must be taken into account.

MATERIAL AND TEST PROCEDURE

The material used in this study is quasi-unidirectional Glass/Epoxy composite (52% vol.) with 5% woven fibers. The elastic constants are summarized in Table 1. The combined tension-torsion tests were carried out in a static tension-torsion machine at room temperature. The specimen ends are fixed in the grips, the rotation speed at a rate of 20°/min and the axial displacement speed at 0.5 mm/min were imposed, this has given a ratio P/M=650 N/N.m obtained experimentally.

Tab.1 Material properties

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{31}	ν_{23}	ν_{32}
36.23	10.62	7.21	5.60	3.68	3.16	0.23	0.33	0.37	0.48

The following experimental information was recorded simultaneously during the tests : applied moment (M_a), rotation angle(φ), applied load(P), axial displacement (δ) and acoustic emission (cumulative counts and amplitude distribution).

PREDICTION OF THE DAMAGE INITIATION

Using the Tsai-Wu criteria based on the stress analysis, we can predict and localize the damage initiation. This criteria requires a rigorous identification of each stress so as to determine the critical place where the stresses are maximum.

- in the middle and surface of the plate, τ_{12} is maximum, $\tau_{13} = 0$ and $\sigma_{11} \neq 0$, the criteria is expressed by:

$$F_1 \sigma_{11} + F_{11} \sigma_{11}^2 + F_{66} \tau_{12max}^2 = 1 \quad (8)$$

- in the edge and a half-thickness of the plate, τ_{13} is maximum, $\tau_{12} = 0$ and $\sigma_{11} \neq 0$, the criteria become :

$$F_1 \sigma_{11} + F_{11} \sigma_{11}^2 + F_{55} \tau_{13max}^2 = 1 \quad (9)$$

The table 2 presents the values of interaction terms determined experimentally, where F_{55} and F_{66} values were obtained by bending tests.

Tab.2 Tsai-Wu criteria coefficients for Glass/Epoxy

F_{11} (GPa) ⁻²	F_1 (GPa) ⁻¹	F_{22} (GPa) ⁻²	F_2 (GPa) ⁻¹	F_{12} (GPa) ⁻²	F_{44} (GPa) ⁻²	F_{55} (GPa) ⁻²	F_{66} (GPa) ⁻²
2.459	-0.6689	308.30	19.89	-13.77	1625.91	369.25	487.31

The application of this criteria gives two curves (Fig.3) corresponding respectively in the middle and the edge of the plate to the prediction of the damage initiation with equations 8 and 9.

Fig.3 Local application of the Tsai-Wu criteria

The criteria was firstly reached in the middle and surface of the plate corresponding to the angle $\varphi = 9.6^\circ$ ($M_a \approx 15 \text{ N.m}$, $P \approx 10300 \text{ N}$), and secondly the damage progress toward the edges. In order to confirm this prediction and to obtain the direct information on the local degradation, a specimen section was observed after 10° rotation ($M_a \approx 15.4 \text{ N.m}$ and $P \approx 11000 \text{ N}$) by means of a scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Photograph 1 shows the appearance of the microcrackings caused by shear stress τ_{12} . This observation confirms that the Tsai-Wu criteria can be applied to predict the damage initiation. Too, the use of the acoustic emission gives a proof as shown in Fig.4, the beginning of acoustic emission corresponds to an angle 9.7° that is in excellent agreement with the prediction by Tsai-Wu criteria.

Photograph 1 Microscopic observation in the section toward the surface ($\varphi=10^\circ$ $P=11000 \text{ N}$)

Fig.4 Experimental curves and determination of damage initiation by A.E.

DAMAGE ANALYSIS

(a) Damage evolution

After damage initiation, the study of the amplitude distribution of the acoustic emission can help us to identify separately damage mechanisms and their evolution [7,8]. The amplitude distribution corresponding to a given loading is divided into 5 significant ranges where every one of them represents a damage mechanism (Fig.5), called "schematic model"[9,10,11].

Fig.5 Schematic model of acoustic emission for damage identification

In the case of combined tension-torsion, the damage evolution is clearly shown in figure 6 using the schematic model.

Fig.6 Evolution of the damage mechanisms

* $\phi=10^\circ$, $P=11000N$, damage occurs in the resin ($N^\circ 1$), their coalescence ($N^\circ 2$) and interface fracture ($N^\circ 3$) appear in the middle and surface of the plate. This mechanism has been confirmed by the photograph 1.

- * $\varphi=30^\circ$, $P=33000\text{N}$, delamination ($N^\circ 2$) and interface fracture ($N^\circ 3$) are relatively important,
- * $\varphi=50^\circ$, $P=46000\text{N}$, fiber fracture (N°) start in the edges where tensile stress created by combined loading is maximum. Photograph 2 taken under this loading shows clearly the microcrackings, interface and fiber fracture.
- * $\varphi=60^\circ$, $P=53000\text{N}$, a peak situated in 64 dB or thereabouts is distinguished from the mechanism $N^\circ 3$. It express the delamination caused by interface fracture, this degradation was visually observed in the process of test.
- * $\varphi=80^\circ$, $P=58000\text{ N}$, macroscopic fracture occurs in the plate edges, all damage mechanisms were observed.

It is difficult to separate the damage mechanisms due to the tensile and those due to the torsion. A comparative study between combined loading and pure loading (tension, torsion) is necessary.

Photograph 2 Microscopic observation to the edge and a half-thickness ($\varphi=50^\circ$ and $P=46000\text{N}$)

(b) Stiffness variation

Because the damage is caused by combined tension-torsion loading, the global damage must be evaluated by shear modulus G_{12} and compliance $C=\delta/P$, loading/unloading tests were performed. The global damage development expressed in terms of D can be determined by the relationships :

$$\text{with compliance } C : D=1-C/C_0 \tag{10}$$

$$\text{with modulus } G_{12} : D=1-G_{12}/G_{12}^0$$

where C_0 and G_{12}^0 are initial values, and G_{12} is obtained using only the effective moment M_{eff} :

$$G_{12} = (M_{\text{eff}}/\varphi) [L / \beta(c)Wb^3] \tag{11}$$

If the global damage is represented by the compliance variation (Fig.7a), we find that the compliance C loses 9% in the test end; if the global damage is evaluated by shear modulus G_{12} , an important reduction is shown in the figure 7b, 80% lose is due to principal damage taken place in the matrix which affects clearly the shear modulus G_{12} .

Fig.7a Lose of compliance C

Fig.7b Lose of modulus G_{12}

(c) Damage Participation Rate "R_{ij}" and Stiffness variation

In order to identify quantitatively the different damage types and to follow them in the process of tests, a parameter R_{ij}, called "Damage Participation Rate", defined as a ratio of acoustic emission events based on the A.E. model (Fig.5) has been proposed [9,10,11] :

$$R_{ij} = \frac{(\text{Events Numbers})_{ij}}{\text{Total Events to the fracture}} = \frac{m_{ij}}{m_R} \quad (12)$$

- m : event numbers recorded during the tests,
- i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, different damage types numbered by schematic model (Fig.5),
- j : different levels of loads (j = α, β, γ, ...r),
- m_R : event numbers corresponding to the fracture.

So, the parameter R_{ij} express damage state of materials. For the given loading levels, (given j), we have :

$$\begin{aligned} \sum R_i &= 0 && \text{undamaged} \\ 0 < \sum R_i &< 1 && \text{damaged} \\ \sum R_i &= 1 && \text{total fracture} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Using this parameter, the figure 8 shows the evolution of each damage type during the combined tension-torsion loading.

Fig.8 Evolution of each damage type

The damage appears in φ=10° (δ=0.25 mm) under microcracking form (N°1), its coalescence (N°2) and the interface fracture (N°3). The fiber fracture (N°5) becomes significant from φ=60° (δ=1.5mm) and reaches 4% of global damage in the test end. We note that, from the beginning of material degradation, the damage is principally composed by the microcracking coalescence (N°2) creating the delamination, and 42% of its participation rate in the test end. The damage type N°4 (fiber/matrix friction) is also important because of combined tension-torsion loading. This figure gives a quantitative analysis of the damage mechanisms.

The correlation between the damage mechanisms R_{ij} and the stiffness variation (C and G₁₂) allows to distinguish the damage mechanisms which are responsible for the material degradation (Figs.8a and 8b). The compliance C decreases slow from test start (0.5%, see Fig.8a) while the shear modulus G₁₂ loses 33% (Fig 8b). The latter is due essentially to the presence of delamination which is in fact the principal cause of material degradation.

From these figures, it is easy to determine the damage participation rate from a given decrease of the stiffness.

Fig.8 Damage participation rate versus stiffness variation

CONCLUSION

- An unidirectional composite plate under tension-torsion loading is subjected to shear stresses τ_{12} and τ_{13} in addition to the normal stress $\sigma(\phi, y, P)$ which is from the tension and one part of the torsion moment. The maximum tension stress is reached at the ends of the specimen and the minimum at the center of the specimen. If the rotation is important, this normal stress due to torque moment must be taken into account.
- The Tsai-Wu criteria can be used to predict the damage initiation, F_{55} and F_{66} must be determined by 3 points bending tests.
- A schematic model of acoustic emission allows to identify separately damage mechanisms and their evolution. The correlation between damage participation rate R_{ij} and the stiffness variations gives some useful information in improvement of the strength in composite structures.

REFERENCES

1. M.-H.R.Jen, Y.S.Kau and J.M.Hsu, Initiation and propagation of delamination in a centrally notched composite laminate, *J.of Comp. Mat.* **24**, 456-481, (1993)
2. N.L.Hancox, The compression strength of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced plastic" *J. Mater. Sci.* **10** (2).234-242 (1975)
3. N.Sato, T.Kurauchi and O.Kamigaito, Fracture mechanism of unidirectional carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy resin composite, *J. of Mat. Sci.*, **21**, 1005-1010, (1986)
4. A.Laksimi, X.L.Gong and M.L.Benzeggagh, Damage mechanisms analysis in a centrally notched Glass-fiber/Epoxy plate, *Comp. Sci. and Tech*, Vol. **52**. 85-91 (1994).
5. X.L.Gong, A.Laksimi, D.Lai and M.L.Benzeggagh, Stress analysis in unidirectional composite plates under torque loadings : Experimental observation, *J. of Rein.Plas.and Comp.* **14**. (1995).
6. S.G.Lekhnitskii , *Theory of elasticity of an anisotropic elastic body*, Edited by Julius J.Brandstatter, Holden-Day, Inc. san francisco, 197-205 (1963).
7. S.Barré and M.L.Benzeggagh, On the use of acoustic emission to investigate damage mechanisms in Glass-fiber-reinforced polypropylene, *Comp.Sci.and Tech*, Vol.**52**. 369-376 (1994)
8. M.Wevers, I.Verpoest, E.Aernoudt and P.De Meester, Analyse de l'endommagement par fatigue dans les éprouvettes en composites carbone-époxyde avec l'émission acoustique, *Annales des Comp.* 1986 3/4 émi.acous. et mat. comp. Paris, 285-291 (1986).
9. X.L.Gong, A.Laksimi, and M.L.Benzeggagh, Experimental methodology of damage analysis in glass/epoxy plates with circular hole, *JNC 8, Palaiseau.France* 425-436 (1992)
10. X.L.Gong, A.Laksimi, D.Lai and M.L.Benzeggagh, Damage analysis in Glass/Epoxy plates containing a circular hole under torque loading, *JNC 9,Saint-Etienne*,687-697 (1994)
11. X.L.Gong, Développement d'une méthodologie expérimentale associée à une approche analytique pour la compréhension du comportement de plaques composites non-trouées et trouées sous chargement simple et combiné de traction-torsion, *Doctoral Thesis, Université de Technologie de Compiègne, France* , N° : D 741 (1994)